

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarc@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela, Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'. Kasthuri P. K.		217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port Cty	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayanīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेन्द्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुसंधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशवमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14633607>

Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective

Dr. V Vasanthakumari¹

The ability to create something new comes from our desire. According to the Upanisads, the entire creation is the result of the desire of Brahman- सोऽकामयत (Aitareyopanisad I-1-1) The soul's earthly thought is the route of a desire. Desire is the seed of the mind. He thought, let me create the world - स ईक्षत लोकान्नु सृज इति (Bṛhadaranyakopanisad sbh- I-2-1), let me be endowed with a mind; by means of this self, let me have a mind आत्मन्वी आत्मवान् स्याम्। अहमनेन आत्मना मनसा मनस्वी स्याम्।

The mind is one of the most discussed phenomena by philosophers and scientists. What is the 'mind'? How does it function? What is its nature? Philosophers and scientists engage in serious discussions on these questions. The study of the mind, its functions, and its influence on one's behaviour is psychology. By the end of the 18th century psychology became acknowledged as a distinct academic field. Every school of philosophy has contributed significantly to psychology, logic, ethics, and other mental sciences. But these have never been treated as distinct fields of study in ancient India. According to Swami Akhilananda "Indian psychology has grown out of religious concepts, that is, the reason that it basically clarifies the philosophy of life. It not only gives conceptual knowledge of the different states of mind and their functioning but it also teaches us how emotions can be unified, redirected and integrated". Before the establishment of Psychology as an independent empirical science in

1 Professor, Dept. of Sanskrit Vedanta, SSUS Kalady

1879, it was a part of philosophy (Sinha 25) .

However, research indicates that our ācāryas had in-depth knowledge of these disciplines and expressed their views through their writings. Among them, Śrī Sankara's explanations should be studied seriously. The birth of Śrī Śankara, who laid the foundation of Advaita in Kerala, is a blessing for the state. Through his sacred birth, Advaita got its roots in Kerala and through his doctrines, he paved the route for its growth and success. He had an extensive knowledge of Indian knowledge systems.

In addition to metaphysics, Indian philosophical literature is abundant in the fields of psychology, logic, ethics, aesthetics, and epistemology. Here we find a synthetic treatment of a problem in all its multifarious aspects. The Psychological problems of perception i.e. perception of the self, perception of the universal etc., are unintelligible without consideration of their metaphysical foundations. In his Sarva vedanta siddhānta sārāsamgraha Śrī Śankara says मनः प्रमादः पुरुषस्य बन्धो मनः प्रसादो भवबन्धमुक्तिः । i.e. where there is turbulence in the mind, there is nothing but bondage. But where there is tranquillity, liberation is at hand. That means that the mind is a cause or an extraordinary instrument for bondage and liberation. A pure mind is the cause of liberation, whereas an impure mind is the cause of bondage. बन्धश्च मोक्षो मनसैव पुंसां (Sarvavedantasiddhanta sarasamgraha- 358.) ।' As a Sarvajña, Śrī Śankara has given an explanation on mind and its functions vividly. He defines the mind as मन्वानो मनो मनुत इति, i.e., as it thinks, the mind. Here, the self thinks in the capacity of the doer. The mind is endowed with the power of mentation मनो मनस्यनविशिष्टमन्तःकरणम् (Chandogyopanisad. VII-3-1). ' It is a frequently used instrument for the expansion of the power of knowledge. The mind is antahkaraṇa. It is the cause of all that we perceive because nothing exists when the antahkaraṇa does not exist and everything exists when it does. Śrī Sankara states that the mind is indeed infinite in its different behaviours वृत्तिभेदेनानन्तम्। Consciousness is the nature of the mind and so it is established in the form of Self. As it is an instrument of knowledge, it is antahkaraṇa. According to Guru Nityacaitanya Yati, consciousness

is the limit of inquiry about soul, mind and body (Nityachaitanya Yati, Bharatiyamanasastrattinoramukham- P-10.).

Sri Sankara clearly describes the origin of the antahkarana. It emanates from the interaction of five satva parts, which are present in the ākaśa, vāyu and the like. आकाशादिगताःपञ्चसात्विकांशाः परस्परं मिलित्वैव 37-7: करणमभवत्सर्वकारणम् ।⁷ Even though antahkarana is one, it undergoes various modifications according to the nature of the function that it discharges. From functional point of view, it is known as the manas, buddhi, ahankara and chitta. When engaged in reflection it is known as the mind; when forming a resolution it is called the buddhi. When permeated by self- love, as ahankara and when recognizing known object, it is known as chittam. मनश्च पूर्वोक्तम्, मन्तव्यं च तद्विषयः, बुद्धिश्च निश्चयात्मिका, बोद्धव्यं च तद्विषयः, अहङ्कारश्च अभिमानलक्षणमन्तः करणमहङ्कर्तव्यं च तद्विषयः, चित्तं च चेतनावदन्तः करणम् । (Sarvavedantasiddhanta sarasamgraha- 342)

Reflecting upon and recognising non-objects together constitute the function of the mind. It is only natural that the mind should merge with consciousness. According to Śrī Sankara, among these fourfold divisions, buddhi is the agent and the Mind is the instrument of action. Buddhi (intellect) is the authority in the understanding of the real nature of the existent and the non-existent - बुद्धिर्हि नः प्रमाणं सदसत्तोर्याथात्म्यावगमने । Cittam means comprehension- चित्तं चेतयितृत्वम्, i.e., comprehension of something in relation to a specific time, as also the capability of investigating into the merit of an object of the past and future.

Origin of the mind

In his Chandogya and Bṛhadaraṇyakopaniṣad bhāṣyas, he describes the origin of the mind. The digestive fire in the abdomen separates the food that has been consumed into three portions. Of these three parts, the grossest part becomes excreta, the middle part transforms into the essence that finally becomes flesh and the subtlest part becomes the mind. It becomes transformed into the mind and strengthens it. He also states that the mind is a transformation of food, so, it has a purely, materialistic source. -अन्नोपचितत्वात् मनसः भौतिकत्वमेव (Chandogyopaniṣad.sbh. VI-5-2).

That mental strength developed by food is divided into sixteen

parts (षोडशकलाः) of a man - षोडशकलपुरुषः Man in the particular aspect as jīva endowed with the aggregate of the body and senses and the mental strength developed through food and divisible into sixteen parts, is said to consists of sixteen parts. These sixteen parts are discussed in Praśnopaniṣad bhāṣya (Prasnopanisad. VI-4): prāṇa, śraddhā, ākāśa, vāyu, Agni, jalam, prthivi, indriyam, manah and annam vīryam, tapah, mantra, karma and lokah, and lokesu nāma. When endowed with this strength man becomes drastā, śrotā, mantā, boddhā, kartā etc. Śrī Śankara argues that people with mental strength are powerful in the world. The skillfulness of the body and senses results from the mind alone- मानसेन हि बलेन सम्पन्ना बलिनो दृश्यन्ते लोके (Chandogyopanisad.sbh. VI-7-1).

Manas, prāṇa and vāk are inseparable. Mentation (मनस्यनं) arises when one thinks about what ought to be done - विभागेन हि समर्थिते विषये चिकीर्षाबुद्धिः मनस्यनं Thus endowed with the function of mentation, it urges speech when utterance is to be made. Speech is inherent in the mind.

Existence of the mind

In his Brhadāranyakopaniṣad bhāṣya Śrī Śankara logically establishes the existence of the mind. He claims that without it, even the eye, ear, and other sense organs that can perceive form, sound, and the like are ignorant of their respective objects, namely form, sound, and the like, and in the presence of which they do it, is understood to be the internal organ called the mind. It is different from all other organs and is in contact with all organs.

There is a mind different from external senses such as the ear, because it is well known that even when the external senses objects and the Self are in close contact, a man's vision does not catch the object towards which his face remains turned. When asked, have you seen this form? He replies, my mind was elsewhere and it being elsewhere, I did not see. Similarly, when asked – did you hear what I said? He replies that my mind was elsewhere and so I did not hear- अस्ति तावन्मनः श्रोत्रादिबाह्यकरणव्यतिरिक्तं, यत एवं प्रसिद्धं- बाह्यकरणविषयात्मसम्बन्धे सत्यपि अभिमुखीभूतं विषयं न गृह्णाति, किं दृष्टवानसीदं रूपम्? इत्युक्तो वदति अन्यत्र मे गतं मन आसीत् सोऽहमन्यत्र मना आसं नादर्शम् (Brhadaranyakopanisad sbh- I-5-

3) | Therefore, through the mind the entire world sees and hears since there can be no vision when the mind is intently occupied. He highlights an additional rationale for the existence of the mind. He asserts that discrimination stems from the existence of the mind. He explains this with an example: When one is touched even from behind without coming before one's eyes, one knows through discrimination that this is a touch of the hand or of the knee, therefore the mind exists-चक्षुषो ह्यगोचरे दृष्टतोऽप्युपस्पृष्टः केनचित् हस्तस्यायं स्पर्शो जानोरयमिति विवेकेन प्रतिपद्यत । यदि विवेककृन्मनो नाम नास्ति तर्हि त्वङ्गमालेण कुतो विवेकप्रतिपत्तिः स्यात्? Knowledge is nonsimultaneous. This also proves the existence of the mind.

Nature of Mind

According to Śrī Śankara mind is of the nature of snkalpa, vikalpa, samsaya, nirnaya and the like. Bṛhadāraṇyakopaniṣad says that kāma, sankalpa, vicikitsā, śraddhā, aśraddhā, dhṛti, adhṛti, hrī, dhī, bhī etc. are the different forms of the mind कामः सङ्कल्पो विचिकित्सा श्रद्धा श्रद्धाधृतिरधृतिहीर्षाभीरित्येतत्सर्वं (Bṛhadaranyakopanisad sbh- I-5-3.) says that it is as a result of the functioning of the mind that one feels anxiety, dejection, joy, and desire. Through the instrumental agency of the mind one seeks in the external world, the benefit of all that one strives for. The mind is therefore the cause of both work and enjoyment- चिन्ताविषादहर्षाद्याः कामाद्याः अस्य वृत्तयः । मनुते मनसैवैव फलं कामयते बहिः (Sarvavedantasiddhanta sarasamgraha- 356).

It is a serious question to ask whether the mind is an independent entity. In his Kenopaniṣad bhāṣya he says that the mind is not independent, because if the mind were independent, in the matter of pravṛtti and nivṛtti then none would ever have any thought of evil. Without the light of the consciousness, the antahkaraṇa will not be able to perform its functions such as thinking and determining- नह्यन्तःकरणम् अन्तरेण चैतन्यज्योतिषो दीधितिं स्वविषयसङ्कल्पाध्यवसायादिसमर्थं स्यात् । The cognition of a thing takes place indeed through the combined functions of the senses and the mind. It is not possible that by mind everything becomes thinkable because what is thinkable is impossible to be thought of without the thinker - सर्वमपि मन्तव्यं मन्तारमन्तरेण न मनुं शक्यम् (Aitareyopanisad. Sbh. II-1).

Mind alone is the atma because it is only when the mind is active the self becomes an agent and enjoyer; not otherwise. Hence, the mind is said to be the Self - “मनो ह्यात्मा”. -Waking or dreaming of the Self (jīva) is caused by its being conditioned by the mind. Brhadaranyakopanisad says: associating with the mind and becoming identified with the dream, it meditates, as it were, it moves, as it were. In the real sense, the self does not dream or keep awake, by itself. The mind first observes an object, then makes an effort and finally accepts it. Buddhi supports the mind in its activity. The triguṇas affect the functioning of both the mind and the Buddhi. He states that it is logical to say that the mind is independent while experiencing diverse forms - मनसः विभूत्यनुभवे स्वातन्त्र्यवचनं न्याय्यमेव (Prasnopanisad. Sbh IV-5). It is a means in the matter of the acquisition of the knowledge of Brahman- मनसैवेदम् आप्तव्यम् ।

In the Aitareyopanisad, it is stated that the heart is the mind- यदेतत् हृदयं मनश्चैतत् (III-1-2) - through this one antahkaraṇa, as associated with the eye, one sees forms; as associated with the ear, one hears; as associated with the sense of smell, one smells; as associated with the sense of taste, one tastes; through this alone in its mental aspect as characterised by doubt, one doubts, and in its aspects as the intellect one determines. Therefore, this is the one instrument that functions embracing all objects of senses, rendering every perception of the perceiver possible- एतेन अन्तःकरणेन एकेन चक्षुर्भूतेन रूपं पश्यति श्रोत्रभूतेन शृणोति घ्राणभूतेन जिघ्रति वाग्भूतेन वदति जिह्वाभूतेन रसयति स्वेनैव विकल्पनारूपेण मनसा विकल्पयति हृदयरूपेण अध्यवस्यति । Here Śrī Sankara says that the self, for whose perception the functions of the internal organ in the form of the heart and the mind are to be explained- Samjanam- perception, the state of consciousness, Ājñānam- command; vijñānam- knowledge of the arts and the like; prajñānam: alertness of the mind; medhā: power of grasping and retaining in memory the essence of texts; Dṛṣṭi: perception of all objects through the senses; Dhṛti: firmness that breaths vigour into the weary body and senses; mati: power of reflection, manīṣā: freedom of thinking; jūti: mental affliction resulting from illness, smṛti: memory, sankalpa: ascertainment of forms etc., kratu: determination; asu: act of respiration that sustains the activity of life; kāma: longing; vasa: fascination with keeping company with women.

The internal organ, the means of perception of the witness, is a limiting adjunct of Brahman. अन्तःकरणवृत्तयः प्रज्ञप्तिमात्रस्य उपलब्धुः उपलब्ध्यर्थत्वात् शुद्धप्रज्ञानरूपस्य ब्रह्मणः नामधेयानि भवन्ति (Aitareyopanisad sbh. III-1-2). He adds that all of them becomes the names of consciousness, but not naturally and directly- 'सर्वाण्येव प्रज्ञानस्य नामधेयानि भवन्ति न स्वतः साक्षात्'. All these indicate that the mind has two divisions: śuddha and aśuddha (Pure and impure). The mind free from contact with the external senses is the pure mind, i.e., the self.

Compared to other sense organs the 'mind' is the divine, supernatural, extraordinary eye of the Self, by which one sees. Hence it is called 'daivam caksu'. It is the instrument of perception of objects over all three periods of time. Similar to this it is free from evil. It is the means of perception of everything subtle and hidden. Hence, it is called the divine eye. मनस्तु त्रिकालोपलब्धिकरणं मृदितदोषं च सूक्ष्मव्यवहितादिसर्वोपलब्धिकरणं चेति दैवं चक्षुरुच्यते (Chandogyopanisad.sbh. VII-12-5). It is pure mind. Bondage and liberation are alike of the mind; so the two are good and evil. Mokṣa is the result of a pure mind; bandha is the result of an impure mind. शुद्धेन मोक्षो मलिनेन बन्धो । विवेकतोऽर्थोप्यविवेकतोऽन्यः (Sarvavedantasiddhanta sarasamgraha- 358) ।

The tranquillity of the mind leads to knowledge, and through this, one can attain mokṣa. Mokṣa is not simply a negative state but a condition characterised by positive factors of bliss, knowledge and existence. Psychological knowledge is to be utilised for the attainment of this highest state. Śrī Śankara's perspectives on the mind and its functions can be considered intensely practical i.e. a way of life. To understand the mind and keep it filled with positive thoughts alone is the way to spiritual elevation. The Indian mind often draws inspiration from great souls and considers them role models to be elevated. Hence Śrī Śankara's explanation of the mind and its functions may be studied to uncover new perspectives in Indian psychological studies.

Works Cited

- Sastri, Govinda. *Ten principal Upanisads: with Sankarabhāṣya*. Motilal Banarsidass, 1978.
- Sinha, Durganand. *Psychology for India*. SAGE Publications, 2015.
- Yati, Nitya Chaithanya. *Bharatiya Manasastrathinu Oramukham*. 3 ed., Kottayam, DC Books, 2015.

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,